

GLOSSARY

Epistemic Insight

Knowledge about knowledge, particularly knowledge about disciplines and how they interact.

Big Questions that bridge science, religion and the wider humanities

Big Questions that bridge science, religion and the wider humanities include questions like, 'Why do life and the universe exist?' 'Can a robot be a good friend?; and 'Does God control the weather?'

These are questions about human personhood and the nature of reality that stretch across discipline boundaries and across subject boundaries in schools. They are also questions on which both science and religion seem to have something to say.

Big Questions

The phrase 'Big Questions' is widely used and can mean different things to different people and at different times even if we limit our scope to Big Questions discussed in school.

Teachers may use the phrase, 'Big Question' to draw attention to an important question in their subject e.g. a Big Question in a history lesson could be 'Why is the search for truth about the past flawed but nonetheless of great importance?' a geography teacher might say that a Big Question for a geographer is 'How does where we live affect our health?' There are also Big Questions that bridge subjects and disciplines such as 'What is the future for air travel?'

Most disciplines and subjects have something to say about most questions ... but each of the different disciplines have their preferred questions, methods and norms of thought.

Disciplines

A branch or field of knowledge that is studied. To help young people to become familiar with the word 'discipline', they could consider and discuss examples on their timetable such as: Science, history, geography, and mathematics.

Subjects

A school subject may focus on working with one discipline or it may cover more than one.

Discipline Wheel

An epistemological tool which has a space for a question in the centre of a wheel of disciplines. If the question is a Big Question like 'what does it mean to be alive?' then students could be invited to think critically about how each of the disciplines around the wheel could help them to investigate the question. Or if the question is a more focused question, students could be asked to consider which of the disciplines would be particularly important to work with.

Multidisciplinary questions

Multidisciplinary questions are investigated by drawing on three or more disciplines. Which disciplines could help us to investigate the question, "Why do we wear shoes?"

Bridging question

A question that is pedagogically engineered (designed by the teacher) to bridge two disciplines. An example is "Why did the Titanic sink?" which bridges science and history so that students can compare and contrast how each discipline interprets the question, investigates the question, arrives at (various) answer(s) and evaluates each answer to see if it is a good answer.

Bridging questions might be posed by teachers who are specialists in order to elucidate what is the proper activity for that discipline, and what is not, and perhaps why a multidisciplinary investigation is called for.

Science questions

Science addresses questions about the natural world (rather than the social world) which we can investigate by gathering observations to build and test ideas. Or in other words, science questions can be investigated empirically using the methods of science.

Observation

Science begins from observations of the natural world and moves on to construct ways (theories) to explain our observations.

Scientific knowledge

A good answer in science helps us to understand how the natural world works and is supported by repeatable observations and measurements.

The Natural world

Science investigates and helps us to understand how the natural world works. Questions about the natural world deal with the building blocks of nature such as fire, water, land, air, minerals, plants and all living things. (matter and energy and how they are organised).

www.naturaluniversalsecrets.com/blog/what-does-the-natural-world-include-top-10-list

The Real World

In education we refer to real-world problems and the nature of reality to highlight the complexity of reality. The real world is more complex than we can currently understand in scholarship and more complex than we can understand in school.

The world around us

This phrase is widely used in education to refer to an area of learning addressed by Geography, History, and Science and Technology. See for example www.bbc.co.uk/bitesize/subjects/zr3t4wx

Bubble tool

An epistemological tool, which considers the level of amenability a question has to science.

Disciplinary / Epistemic knowledge

Knowledge about disciplines and the questions, methods and norms of thought specific to them. Developing an appreciation of the strengths and limitations of individual disciplines.

Scholar

A person who pursues a field of study to develop expert knowledge / experiential appreciation about how the discipline works and what sorts of outcomes can be expected.

Strengths and limitations of a discipline

Questions about the strengths and limitations of a discipline are addressed by considering what sorts of questions are preferred by a discipline. Also, by considering how effective a disciplines' methods and norms of thought are in responding to a question.

A question that is amenable to science

'Does the size of a parachute affect how quickly an object falls to earth?' (We can come up with an idea about how the natural world works and make predictions and decide what can be measured, observed and repeated.)

Methods: Scientists use many methods in their work but one that is central and discussed at school is called the scientific method. It involves designing systematic investigations that manipulate variables to generate observations that are thought relevant to the initial question and related hypothesis.

In school science the important issue of where these questions come from is not discussed as much as it could be because the questions that children explore are often those given in textbooks or other materials which have been prepared for the student to work with. It requires creativity and expertise to frame and design a question that is a good one for science.

